

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Arařtırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

كتاب المتون الكاملة للمؤتمر الدولي السادس للتنمية المستدامة والمجال

Book of Proceedings 6th International Congress on Sustainable Development and Space

Editörler - المحررون - Editors

Sami Baskın, Sid Ahmed Soufiane

08-11 Ekim/October 2024 - Ankara/Türkiye

ISBN: 978-625-98855-5-1

Yayımlanma tarihi (published date): 15.10.2024

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

كتاب المتون الكاملة للمؤتمر الدولي السادس للتنمية المستدامة والمجال

Book of Proceeding's 6th International Congress on Sustainable Development and Space

Editörler (Editor): Sami Baskın, Sid Ahmed Soufiane

Kapak Fotoğrafı:

KÜTÜPHANE BİLGİ KARTI

1. Basım, Elektronik Kitap (Çevrim içi / Web tabanlı)

210 x 297 mm

Kaynakça var, dizin yok.

ISBN 978-625-98855-5-1

1. Kongre Tam Metinleri 2. Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma 3. Enerji ve Ekoloji

Yayımlanma adresi: <https://saybildercongress.com/isd/>

Recent Academic Studies Publishing

Yeni Pazar Mh. Ali Okumuş Cad. Mevlana Sitesi A Blok – Çayeli / Rize

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

Kongre Onursal Başkanı - Honorary President

Prof. Dr. İbrahim Özcoşar - Rector of Mardin Artuklu University, Türkiye
Prof. Dr. Mehmet Naci Bostancı - Rector of Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli University, Türkiye
Prof. Dr. Mounir Dhouib - Carthage University (Tunisie)

Düzenleme Kurulu / Organizing Board

Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı - Head of the Organizing Board

Prof. Dr. Hüseyin Akyüz - Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli University, Türkiye

Düzenleme Kurulu Üyeleri / Members of the Organizing Board

Prof. Dr. Hatem Fahad Hanoo - University of Mosul - Iraq
Prof. Dr. Muhammad Matarna - Tafila Technical University - Jordan
Prof. Dr. Najem Dhaher - Carthage University - Tunisia
Prof. Dr. Ömer Bozkurt - Mardin Artuklu University - Türkiye
Prof. Dr. Raghad Abdul Karim Ahmed - University of Mosul - Iraq
Prof. Dr. Sid Ahmed Sufyan - University of Annaba - Algeria
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb - October 6 University - Egypt
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Sami Baskın - Tokat Gaziosmanpaşa University - Türkiye
Dr. Esat Layek - Tokat Gaziosmanpaşa University - Türkiye
Dr. Said Assil - Regional Center for Education and Training Professions - Morocco
Dr. Yasser Ahmad - University of Bahrain - Bahrain
Assistant Teacher Firas Talal Ghazal Yahya - University of Mosul - Iraq
Assistant Teacher Luqman Saeed Ibrahim - University of Mosul - Iraq

Üniversite Tarafından Bu Kongre İçin Görevlendirilmiş Düzenleme Kurulu Üyesi*

Prof. Dr. Ömer Bozkurt - Mardin Artuklu University - Türkiye

Değerlendirme Kurulu Başkanı - Head of The Evaluation Board

Prof. Dr. Sid Ahmed Sufyan - University of Annaba - Algeria

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

Değerlendirme Kurulu - Evaluation Board

- Prof. Dr. Abdul Rahman bin Omar bin Ahmed Al-Madkhali - Jazan University - Saudi Arabia
- Prof. Dr. Natali Karkoud Angers University - France
- Prof. Dr. Foued Benghodban Oum El Bouaghi University - Algeria
- Prof. Dr. Najem Daher Carthage University - Tunisia
- Prof. Dr. Sid Ahmed Bellel Oran 2 University - Algeria
- Dr. Abdallah Ali Azzalab Sanaa University - Yemen
- Dr. Amer Shakir Al-Kinani University of Baghdad - Iraq
- Dr. Bachiri Hamza Centre Nationale De La Recherche En Anthropologie Sociale Et Culturelle, Crasc, Oran - Algeria
- Dr. Badreddine Rouass Universite Abdelah Esaadi - Morocco
- Dr. Bouchetta Khazen Fes University - Morocco
- Dr. Bousmaha Ahmed Oum El Bouaghi University - Algeria
- Dr. Gouassmia Asma Souk Ahras University - Algeria
- Dr. H. Burçin Helden Şolt - Zonguldak Bülent Ecevit University - Turkiye
- Dr. Mouhamed Mouhamed El Moughir Ghaza University - Palestine
- Dr. Mustafa Kemal Sen Sakarya Üniversitesi
- Dr. Nassier Abbas Ghubin Al-Zubaidi University of Baghdad - Iraq
- Dr. Nihad Hasan Haji (Al Shemri) Wasit University - Iraq
- Dr. Orora Lopez Acona Zaragoza University - Spain
- Dr. Ouadiaa Othmani Angers University - France
- Dr. Shukri Abd Elmageed Saber Cairo University - Egypt
- Dr. Sid Ahme Soufiane Anaaba University - Algeria
- Dr. Sid Salah Biskra University - Algeria
- Dr. Tarig Hamdnaalla Ahmed Hamadnalla Higher Council For Environment, Urban And Rural Promotion- Khartoum State -Sudan
- Dr. Zekri Nadia Aboubeker Belkaid University - Algeria

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

مقدمة

يواجه العالم تحديات كبيرة في إقامة توازن بين التنمية المستدامة والحفاظ على البيئة من جهة ومن جهة أخرى تحقيق الأمن الغذائي والذي أصبح من أولويات الدول بفعل الاحتكار واختلال التوازن بين الطلب والإنتاج، ففي الوقت الذي يواصل فيه الاعتماد على الطرق التقليدية في الزراعة المعتمدة أساساً على تساقط الأمطار والاستهلاك المفرط للمياه الجوفية غير المتجددة، فإن هذا له أثراً كبيراً على نزوب الموارد الاقتصادية غير المتجددة واستقرار الأمن الغذائي بالعالم. ولذلك يتجه العالم إلى مصادر الطاقة المتجددة والبحث عن بدائل تضمن احتياجات السكان وفق مبدأ التنمية المستدامة.

وتعد الطاقة المتجددة بأنها الحل الأخير لمشاكل الطاقة والبيئة في العالم، مما يتيح إمكانية الطاقة الرخيصة وغير المحدودة تقريباً الخالية من التلوث، حيث نجد بأن العالم يستهلك الطاقة من مصادر عديدة، فمنها المصادر التي تأتي من خامات الوقود الأحفوري مثل الفحم والنفط والغاز الطبيعي، ومنها الطاقة التي تأتي من مصادر صناعية مثل الطاقة النووية. كما يحصل على الطاقة أيضاً من مصادر طبيعية مثل الطاقة الشمسية والطاقة المستخلصة من الرياح ومساقط المياه والتي تسمى بمصادر الطاقة المتجددة.

إن المشاكل المتفاقمة من خلال أزمات الطاقة والتخوف من اختلال الأمن الغذائي ولاسيما في الدول الأكثر فقراً، يستوجب إعادة التفكير بشكل جوهري على المستوى الدولي وفق استراتيجيات مستدامة تحقق الاستقرار على مستوى العالم وتجنباً الوقوع في أزمات دولية تتركز أساساً على الاستغلال العقلاني للموارد الطبيعية واعتماد طاقات متجددة وأساليب جديدة في الزراعة لضمان تحقيق استدامة في الأمن الغذائي والحفاظ على حقوق الأجيال القادمة.

د. صيد وحمد سفيان

رئيس اللجنة العلمية

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

Preface

The world faces great challenges in balancing sustainable development and environmental preservation with achieving food security, which has become a priority for countries due to the monopoly and imbalance between demand and production, while continuing to rely on traditional agricultural methods based mainly on rainfall and excessive consumption of non-renewable groundwater, This has a significant impact on the depletion of non-renewable economic resources and the stability of global food security. Therefore, the world is turning to renewable energy sources and is looking for alternatives that guarantee the needs of the population in accordance with the principle of sustainable development.

Renewable energy promises to be the latest solution to the world's energy and environmental problems, allowing for the possibility of cheap and nearly unlimited energy, free of pollution, as we find that the world consumes energy from many sources, including sources from fossil fuel ores such as coal, oil and natural gas, and energy from industrial sources such as nuclear power. It also draws energy from natural sources such as solar, wind and watersheds called renewable energy sources.

The problems exacerbated by the energy crises and the fear of the occupation of food security, especially in the poorest countries, require a fundamental rethinking at the international level in accordance with sustainable strategies that ensure stability at the global level and avoid falling into international crises based mainly on the rational exploitation of natural resources and the adoption of renewable energies and new methods of agriculture to ensure the sustainability of food security and preservation of the rights of future generations.

Prof. Dr. Sid Ahmed Soufiane

President of the Scientific Committee

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

ÖN SÖZ

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi, 08-11 Ekim 2024 tarihlerinde Ankara'da gerçekleşti. Bu kongre, Saybilder Topluluğunun organizasyonunda ve başta Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli Üniversitesi, Mardin Artuklu Üniversitesi, Carthage University olmak üzere çeşitli yükseköğretim kurumlarının ilmi desteği ile düzenlenmektedir. Kongreye 5 farklı ülkeden davetli konuşmacı davet edilmiştir. Aynı zamanda Türkçe, İngilizce ve Arapça duyurular yapılarak bilim insanlarına çağrıda bulunulmuştur. Bu çağrılar sonrasında Türkiye'den 16, Türkiye dışından da 8 ülkeden (Cezayir, Çin, Fas, Libya, Mısır, Suudi Arabistan Krallığı, Tunus, Birleşik Arap Emirlikleri) 53 bildiri yer almaktadır. Tüm bildiriler kör hakemlik sürecinden geçirildikten sonra sunuma kabul veya reddi gerçekleştirilmiştir. Bu süreç içerisinde bildirilerin önemli bir kısmına hakemlerden düzeltme talebi gelmiştir. Hakemler tarafından talep edilen düzeltmelerin yapılıp yapılmadığı da özenle kontrol edilmiş ve düzeltmelerden sonra kabul mektupları düzenlenerek yazarlarına gönderilmiştir. Bu kitapta kongrede sunulan bildire ait tam metinler yer almaktadır.

Kongrenin bilim insanları arasındaki iletişimi kuvvetlendirmesini, bilgi alışverişini arttırmasını, ortak çalışma zeminlerini oluşturmasını, milletimize, insanlığa ve bilgiyle amel edenlere faydalı olmasını diliyorum.

Bu kitapta kongrede sunum yapan bilim insanlarının bildirinin tam metinleri yer almaktadır. Kongreye iştirak edemeyen ve bu konulara ilgi duyan kimselerin metinlerden istifade edebilmesini sağlayacak olan bu çalışmanın bilim dünyasına hayırlara vesile olmasını diliyorum.

15.10.2024

Prof. Dr. Şinasi Akdemir

Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı

İçindekiler - فهرس - Contents

Experimental Study Of Cascade Solar Still 1

H. Menous

S. Allal

A. Bendahou

O. Cheknane

A. Hamid

La résilience territoriale face aux enjeux du développement durable, cas du village lauréat du concours du village le plus propre dans la wilaya de Tizi-Ouzou, Algérie. 10

Karima Idres

Lotfi Mokrani

Kamel Moulai

The Relationship Between Melting and Dripping Behavior of PP Thermoplastic Polymers Due to The Furnace Test 22

Mastura A. Abdoalshafie Efhema

33.....التنمية المستدامة ومجاليات التدوير الفني في تونس: تجربة الفنان الطيب بالحاج أحمد نموذجاً
د. هندة بوحامد

53.....واقع الطاقات المتجددة في تحقيق التنمية المستدامة بالمملكة العربية السعودية"
د.إلهام شيلي

70.....الوكالة الجزائرية لترقية الاستثمار ضمن القانون 18-22
الدكتور لعابسة طارق

85.....التنمية البيئية المستدامة من منظور شرعي
د. جيداء رجب صيام

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

Dergipark'ta "Türkiye'nin Çevre Sorunlarına Yönelik Tutumlar" Başlığı Altında Yapılan Çalışmaların İncelenmesi* 98

Furkan Doğru

Prof. Dr. Asım Çoban

The Relationship Between Melting and Dripping Behavior of PP Thermoplastic Polymers Due To The Furnace Test 114

Mastura A. Abdoalshafie Efhema

Üniversite Öğrencilerinin Çevre Bilincini Ele Alan Çalışmaların İncelenmesi* . 126

Furkan Doğru

Prof. Dr. Asım Çoban

The Relationship Between Melting and Dripping Behavior of PP Thermoplastic Polymers Due To The Furnace Test

Mastura A. Abdoalshafie Efhema

Omar Almhktar university, Al Baida, Aljapal Al Akhdar, Libya

Abstract

This work studies the effect of flame retardants and 1% stabilizer on melting and dripping behaviour. The experimental tools which named electrical furnace has been developed in specific experimental method in 3 stages, the furnace setup developed by 3 phases, which are applied modulated whilst adjusting the furnace set up, ready for the furnace test of melting and dripping in the experimental tests in this present work. In 3 stages, the six polymers were tested to record melt dripping behaviour in real time in an electric furnace. Stage 1 involved swiftly obtaining the furnace's required temperature. After reaching the maximum temperature, stage 2 and 3 the sample is placed in the furnace and weighed using an Ohaus balance. Sample weight is recorded at a specific temperature, Sample weight is recorded at a particular temperature, using a personal computer connected to this Ohaus balance and furnace, the mass loss % versus time can be plotted to draw the curve of this mass loss with time. In this work using the outline of the planned experimental methodology applied to study the melt dripping behaviour of the samples of 7 types Polypropylene (PP) polymers with different FR, blend in twin-screw extruder with 1% stabilizer additive, to investigate the action of different types of FR and additive on melting, dripping behaviour and it's a moderation to reduce these sample melting and dripping, at various furnace temperatures was examined and thus the temperatures of the molten drops dripping from melting surface of the samples, to complete the furnace test and investigation of the parameters effected on the relationship between melting/ dripping behaviour which is the aim of this present work. Melting and dripping behaviour tests using furnace melting and dripping tests conditions were applied in this study after furnace setup developed. The relationship between melting and dripping behaviour could be obtain and proven by experimental results. The molten drops temperatures can help in guessing the degree degradation in a sample of polymer all through melt dripping. By performing thermogravimetric (TGA) analysis of the polymers and their molten drops, a degradation degree will possibly be expected. The values found from both methods TGA and Furnace test have been compared in order to understand the melt dripping and degradation behaviour of polymers to obtain the relationship between melting and dripping behaviour of PP thermoplastic polymers. Most of the previous works on melt and dripping behaviours were concentrated on study of fire operating conditions, and modelling of the thermal process, however no work has been reported on quantitative relationship between melting and dripping behaviour of thermoplastic polymers.

Keywords: polypropylene thermoplastic polymers, flame retardants and additives, polymer melting/dripping behaviour, melting/dripping relationship.

Introduction

This study focused on polypropylene (PP), a valuable commodity polymer with strong mechanical quality, low reactivity toward other chemicals, and common use in floor coverings, clothes, furniture, medical, and automotive applications and high tensile strength at break. The degradation of polypropylene polymer happens at high temperatures; if PP is 100% isotactic, the melting temperature of the polymer is 174 oC, and the glass transition temperature is -17 oC. The major assistance of PP is its exceptional resistance to numerous chemical solvents, acids, and bases due to its manufacturing as an addition polymer from the monomer propylene. But because it has a completely aliphatic hydrocarbon structure, it burns extremely quickly, mostly without producing smoke, and leaves no char behind. The primary benefit of PP is its exceptional resistance to numerous chemical solvents, acids, and bases due to its manufacturing as an addition polymer from the monomer propylene. But because it has a completely aliphatic hydrocarbon structure, it burns extremely quickly, mostly without producing smoke, and leaves no char behind [1]. Reactive flame retardants respond more difficultly [15] with the structure's lack of polar groups. According to additive flame retardants must be applied in substantial quantities (more than 20% w/w) in order to give products, the necessary fire protection. This has an impact on flame retardancy, which rises with increasing radiation and disappears with decreasing radiation [2]. But these excessive amounts of additives lead to issues with polymer manufacturing, especially when it comes to extrusion into thin fibers. The use of adjuvants and synergists, as well as modifications to the polymeric substance, can all affect flame retardancy. It is important to acknowledge that the use of flame retardants as additions results in a lower polymer content in the formulation when compared to the original polymer. In previous paper that nanoclays can be nanodispersed in polypropylene with a proper choice of compatibilizer), although they aid in the development of char and increase the heat stability of polypropylene [2] and help in char formation [3]. Polypropylene including specific % stabilizer additive with small quantity (5%) of FR could cause to self-extinguish. The numerical results will be finally compared with the experimental work [4].

Materials and procedures:

The seven thermoplastic Polypropylene polymers specimens were purchased from commercial sources. After being combined with flame retardants and UV stabilizer (Nor), samples are examined.

Polymer Preparation:

As indicated in Table 1, the 7 polypropylene (PP) samples prepared are PP-Nor 116, PP-APP 107, PP-NOR-NH, PP FR 107, PP Amgard 107, PP 3OB and PP APP 3OB. These seven samples composition (wt%) are blended in twin a Thermoelectric Prism Eurolab 16 twin screw extruder was utilized, which has a temperature profile spanning six heating zones between 179 and 1900C. Prior to pelletizing, the polymer samples (diameter: 1.8 ± 0.2 mm) were gathered prior to pelletising. These 7PP samples blended with additive of 1% Stabilizer (Nor 116) and different FR 5% such as APP, FR245, Amgrad NH and APP. And with Pb Graft 1%, also with 107 and 30B Clay 3%. As recorded in Table 1, sample PP-Nor 116 remain standing PP 100% composition because of no Clay 3%, Graft 1% and FR 5%, blended with. Also, samples of PP-APP 107 and PP 3OB are not

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

blended with FR 5%, in addition, PP APP 3OB sample blended without Graft 1%. Nevertheless, the nanoclays that could be utilized are montmorillonite clay modified with dimethyl and dihydrogenated tallow quaternary ammonium chloride (Cloisite 20A, Southern Clay Products, USA). Its nonpolar alkyl substituents are why this modified clay was selected.

Table 1.

TABLE1, Mass percentages of various components in the formulations where Stabilizer 1% is NOR 116.

Note: ¹FR = APP, NH, FR245, also PP-NOR-NH is PP 107, FR372 or FR245.

Samples	PP%	Clay 3%	Graft 1%	FR (5%)
1- PP-Nor 116	100	---	---	---
2- PP-APP 107	96	107	Polybond (Pb)	---
3- PP-NOR-NH	91	107	Polybond	APP
4- PP FR 107	91	107	Polybond	¹ FR245
5- PP Amgard 107	91	107	Polybond	Amgrad NH
6- PP 3OB	96	3OB	Polybond	---
7- PP APP 3OB	92	3OB	---	APP

Characterisation and Testing

Here it's good to list some of the different previous tests' results [3, 4] for the same samples recorded in table 1, because of their importance in comparison with the results of the current study to build a new scientific conclusion, also to know which of them should be out of Furnace test (table 2).

DTA-TGA thermal analysis:

Thermal analyses are analysed by DTA-TGA (TA Instruments, SDT 2960) simultaneous 20 °C - 600 °C for 10 °C/min, heating rate in atmospheric Oxygen, the different polymers sample size is 10mg [5]. Therefore, have found the following results and conclusion [5]:

The thermal analysis studies will be uses to find out the processing temperature of these formulations, the melting point gives the temperature at the polymer can be processed in the extruder, also it gives the temperature value, useful to know which the polymers can be used in melting and dripping tested by using the UL-94 and the Furnace testes. At this temperature, polymer samples will be burn in UL-94, to observe the melt/drip behaviour studies of the polymers, also to compare all these processing temperature results with results of the polymers samples with different FR. and additives The mass loss % given by the following equation:

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

The Mass Loss % = $(E3/1.75)*100$, Were: $E3 = \text{Initial Mass} = 1.175$ (1)

The flaming and dripping test:

It appears that the specimen thickness somewhat increases the polypropylene (PP) mass of the first drop. This discovery has to do with how polypropylene polymers break down and drip [5]. Thick specimens can withstand higher melt mass weights or longer times without breaking because they have a bigger cross-sectional area and melt strength than thin specimens. [5] Nevertheless, the dropping of PP is tiny. The polymer melts flow easily once the breakdown dramatically lowers the molecular weight. The specimen's surfaces may seep and trickle with the melted wax. Therefore, in UL-94 flaming test, as recorded in previous study, the use of clay along with traditional flame retardants improves both the overall melting and burning with flaming drips [6, 7].

Theoretical and experimental work:

After carrying out the different last tests, the results of the study on the effect of additives, fillers and reinforcements on melting / burning behaviour of polymers, the results will be analysed after test of UL-94 test, DTA-TGA and Furnace test; by using an empirical mode such as the numerical techniques like Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) and Finite Element Analysis (FEA):

Suitable FEA or CFD software packages (e.g. ABAQUS, ANSYS, FLUENT etc.) will be used to model the samples and rebuild the experimental conditions. The three main phases of a typical FEA or CFD analysis are: analysis, post-processing and pre-processing. As we know, preprocessing means the sample's geometry creation, the selection of material's properties e.g. physical properties and the setting up of the boundary conditions. Also, the analysis and the post-processing such as listed results, contour plots etc. are automatically performed by the software. The above modelling techniques will assist in monitoring the specimen behaviour when heated in furnace and all the data and results of the previous work fire tests recorded [6 and 4]. Although the process can be challenging, considering the number of factors involved during fire testing, the results to be obtained will allow a more comprehensive assessment of the samples' flammability. An even more complicated scenario for modelling will be that of the heat/fire damaged samples, since the physical behaviour of the samples will be also assessed. The numerical results will be finally compared with the experimental work [8, 4] in order to observe the influence of heat/fire on the sample itself as well as its physical properties such as intensity/density to draw the relationship between melt viscosity with drops viscosity and melting behaviour by using the suitable numerical models.

Model and theoretical designed for surface temperature assessment:

The size of polymer samples is small 6 mm - 4 mm - 100 mm in judgment with the furnace diameter 25 mm this estimate can be confirmed, a one-dimensional 1D model can be applied to know the samples surface temperature of the melting. In this model the heat of melting and polymer degradation are comprised), furthermore the heat exchange by correlation between the furnace and the sample is small related to that transfer by radiation. The producer of incident heat flux q_t is from the furnace internal walls, actions by radiation transfer of heat on the polymer faces, this heat transfer by conduction within the thermoplastic polymer telling the

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

model is the equilibrium as shown in equation 2. Equations 2 to 8 following a 3 conditions and terms, the first is 1D energy equation explanation and describes melting thermoplastic polymer gasification exactly to decomposition, the second is the energy loss by decomposition and the third is the moving boundary energy loss.

$$z = L/2, \text{ were } L \text{ thickness of sample } (2)$$

$$\rho c p (\partial T / \partial t) = k \partial^2 T / \partial z^2 - H v \, dm / dt - \rho c p W \partial T / \partial z (3)$$

Hence, $T(z, t)$ is solved; where: z the position and t the time, additionally T , Temperature.

$$(V) \text{ Velocity} = W(z, t) = -0z \int dm / dt / \rho \, dz (4)$$

Experimentally set temperatures are the furnace temperature = T_{fce} (as mentioned earliest that sample is injected in a heat up furnace).

Foremost to say that the Boundary conditions, at $z = 0, dT / dz = 0$

$$\text{And at } z = L/2, -k \, dT / dx = \alpha q_{net} (6) \text{ and } q_{net} = \sigma \varepsilon (T_{fce}^4 - T^4)$$

Replaced (q_{net}) value from equation 7 into equation 6:

$$-k \, dT / dx = \alpha \sigma \varepsilon (T_{fce}^4 - T^4) (8)$$

ε of the wall furnace = 1, also (α) absorption coefficient of the polymer, T_{fce} = temperature furnace wall, T = polymer temperature, also, T_a = ambient temperature, t = time. The material properties taken into account [9]. Here is a good way to point out some of previous work results. Most important is mentioned that by applying equation 2, which is solved mathematically. Therefore, the first and third conditions and terms of the equation 2 right side was solved numerically.

Furnace test

Melting and dripping behaviour experimental technique setup:

In previous work [4], the experimental technique setup for inspection and the use of an electric furnace has been developed and industrialised to research the melt dripping behavior of thermoplastic compounded polymers, as illustrated in Fig.1, and then supporting temperature measurement experiments in this furnace test setup in three stages of experimental work.

The six polymers were tried to capture the melt dripping behavior in real time in an electric furnace [4]; these polymers were chosen based on their process of decomposition and the physics properties [9]

The specifics of the melt dripping test, which was created and is utilized in melt dripping investigations, have been previously discussed [10, 11]. Stage 1 involves quickly reaching the necessary temperature in the furnace. The sample is placed into the furnace fitted with an Ohaus balance to measure the sample weight after the maximum temperature is reached (fig. 1).

Sample weight is recorded at a particular temperature, using a personal computer connected to this Ohaus balance and furnace, the mass loss % versus time can be plotted to draw the curve of this mass loss with time.

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

Figure 1.

FIGURE1. outline of the planned experimental methodology, where 1- the polymer sample, 2- is the electric furnace, 3- the scale, 4- wells, 5- sample hooker wire, 6- the furnace stand, 7- the conveyor belt, 8-, the electric wire set at 200°C, 9- wire to circle connections, 10- adjustable temperature controller, 11- personal computer, 12- two transistors, 13- electric point source connection, 14- furnace cover.

Results and discussion:

The data mentioned in tables 2, 3, 4 and 5 shows the time of initial drip doesn't pointedly raise with thickness of samples. First drip mass additionally shows the same results. Melting-induced dripping during combustion, while acknowledged in scientific discourse [10], remains poorly understood. Nonetheless, the possibility of molten droplets sustaining the ignition of the polymer or nearby objects heightens the fire danger. Notably, polymers with small drop diameters, such as polyethylene (PE) and polymethyl

Methacrylate (PMMA), tend to produce bigger drips in inferno scenarios [11]. The viscosity of materials is the most important factor governing their melt dripping behavior, as increasing temperature causes a corresponding decrease in thermoplastic polymer viscosity, due to

Samples	Temperature °c	Thickness (mm)	Width (mm)	Longeth (mm)	MD (g)	TD (s)
Sample 1	600	3	6	40	0.016	11
Sample 1	600	4	6	40	0.015	13
Sample 1	600	6	6	40	0.017	14
Sample 1	600	9	6	40	0.018	15
Sample 2	600	3	6	40	0.016	11
Sample 2	600	4	6	40	0.021	13
Sample 2	600	6	6	40	0.012	14
Sample 2	600	9	6	40	0.014	15

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

increased molecular mobility and concomitant degradation involving bond cleavage and the Table 2.

TABLE 2. Shows the ATD: Average Time of the first Dripping; AMD: average mass of first drops and ADD: Average Diameter of first Drops. These samples, the same samples show in table 1, including repeated number.

ATD (s)	ADD (mm)	AMD (g)
12= same sample 2 repeated	3.2	0.015
14= same sample 4 repeated	3.45	0.017
16= same sample 6 repeated	2.78	0.012
15 =same sample 5 repeated	2.66	0.008

subsequent emergence of shorter polymer chains. As a result, viscosity emerges as a key characteristic, impacted by both temperature and molecular weight [11]. The introduction of flame retardants or other additives exerts a discernible influence on the viscosity of the molten residue during pyrolysis, consequently modulating the melt dripping propensity of the polymer [12, 13]. It is noteworthy that none of the samples under investigation demonstrate ignition or exhibit any signs of combustion at furnace temperatures below 600 °C, as documented in the preceding section. The furnace temperature parameters governing the formation of molten droplets, extrapolated from thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), are informed by antecedent investigations conducted in 2011 [12], which focused on non-polymeric samples subjected to direct fire exposure. Consequently, the average time of initial dripping (ATD), average mass of initial droplets (AMD), and average diameter of initial droplets (ADD) for the two samples under scrutiny are detailed in Table 2, 3, 4, and 5.

Table 3.

TABLE 3. Shows the dripping behaviour data recorded, of samples 1 and 2 as shows in table 1, where TD: Time of the first Dripping; MD: Mass of the first Drop;

It appears that the first drop's PP mass increases less with sample thickness. This conclusion is related to the decomposition mechanism and dripping of PP polymers, as illustrated in tables 2, 3, 4, and 5. The decomposition is investigated through melting, the analyses of TGA tests as described in reference [9]; in these results and others, such as the UL-49 test; and by noting the times and masses for the initial dripping. Also, for PP, the initial dripping time does not rise considerably with specimen thickness. The mass of the first drop appears to display.

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

Table 4.

TABLE 4. Shows the 2 PP samples with 5 various thickness (mm) recorded the TD, Time of the first Drop; MD, Mass of the first Drop; ATD, Average Time of the first Drop; AMD, Average Mass of first Drop; ADD, Average Diameter of first Drop.

Sampil 1				Sample 2				
Polymer	Thickness (mm)	TD {s}	MD (g)	TD {s}	MD (g)	ATD {s}	AMD {g}	ADD {mm}
PP	2	13	0.0158	12	0.0186	12	0.0172	3.3
	4	15	0.0146	14	0.0287	14	0.0217	3.6
	6	16	0.0078	15	0.0147	15	0.0113	2.9
	8	14	0.0067	16	0.0012	15	15 0.0040	2.0
	10	14	0.0086	15	0.0110	15	0.0098	2.8

From the samples TGA melted drops results, the degradation degree has been calculated (equation 9) equally Remaining mass in TGA test melted drops is calculated by measuring the temperature (T50) at which 50% of the mass loss occurs in the sample and defining the corresponding temperature. The difference in ratio residuals indicates degree of degradation in melted drops.

$$\text{Degradation} = \frac{50\% \text{ Mass loss of the polymer on } T50 - \text{mass loss of molted drops on } T50}{50 \times 100} \quad (9)$$

Table 5 shows the analyses results, degree of degradation depends on the types of polymers. Polymer samples as seen as in this table are: Polypropylene PP, Polyamide PA-6, Polycarbonate PC, Polyethylene terephthalate PET, Polystyrene PS and PolyMethyl MethAcrylate PMMA Flame Retardants and 1% Stabilizer as recorded in table 1.

As mentioned in table 5, the data calculating the number of drips and time, masses and diameter for the first dripping is more than the degree of decomposition in Air, to investigate the melting temperature and the melting dripping behaviour for these 6 polymer samples sized 100 x 6 x 4 mm, at these specified furnace setting temperatures selected to avoid any ignites or burn sample, and discovered that the temperature is less than 600 °C.

All these feedback results compared with melted drip achieved on a chosen temperature of the furnace/ pp sample (Figure 1). Melted polymer drops assessed and tested, which have been adjusted at the temperatures of the furnace sites as the following degrees: PP = 600, PA6 = 550, PC = 500, PET = 400, PS = 500 and PMMA = 450 °C, as mentioned in table 5.

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

Table 5.

TABLE 5. Shows the temperatures degree are the ignition temperatures for the 6 samples recorded in table 5.

Polymer samples of (size 100 x 6 x 4 mm)	Temperature of Dripping to starts (°C)	Furnace temperatures chosen for the test of melt dripping (°C)	temperature measurement for the melt drop temperature (°C)	Time of First Melt Drip (s)	Specific Drop mass (mg)	Specific Drop Diameter (mm)	Number of Drops	Degree of Volatilisation (%)	Degree of Decomposition in Air (%)
PP	600	603*	608, 560, 415, 610, 350	5-8	2-5	3-5	52-88	31-40	35.7
PA6	550	610, 425, 495, 560*	610, 400, 375	7-30	18-248	10-15	1-9	30-38	24.4
PC	500	609, 515, 585, 610*	490, 565, 610	4-17	57-70	9-10	6-10	19-23	4.8
PET	400	558, 490, 569*, 600	415, 610, 300, 350	4.4-26	22-163	7-10	6-10	15.3-30	-1
PS	500	580, 548, 570, 573*	600, 450, 500, 609, 550, 576	6.6-13	18-98	8-9	11-18	12-20	24.2
PMMA	450	570, 520, 550, 556*	613, 600, 350, 407	0-48.3	12-30	1.4-3	8-12	40-65	33.3

Conclusions

Following the furnace test results investigation, collected samples data which are recorded in tables 2, 3, 4 and 5; for example, the decomposition in Air, it indicates the difference between total mass loss. As shown in table 5, the data calculating the number of drips and time, masses, and diameter for the first dripping is greater than the degree of decomposition in air. The investigated the melting temperature and melting dripping behaviour for these six polymer samples sized 100 x 6 x 4 mm, at the specified furnace setting temperatures chosen to avoid any ignites or burns, and discovered that the temperature is less than 600 °C. By investigating all these results, specifically

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

those recorded in tables 4 and 5. It gave an advantage to obtain, observe and draw the relationship between melt viscosity and rheology with melt dripping behaviour and melting. The software will automatically complete and apply the analysis of the listed results and charts to the next work. Finally, a side of this work results conclusion, which observed the most important physical properties that affect the melting burning behaviour, which is melt viscosity/rheology. In another hand the degree of the decomposition in Air, to investigate the melting temperature and the melting dripping behaviour , which helps draw the correlation relating melt/drips performance of Polypropylene by applying a specific modelling. The modelling of heat/fire damaged materials will be much more challenging, as the physical behaviour of the samples will be analysed. Finally, the numerical results will be compared to the experimental work to observe the influence of heat/fire on the sample itself as well as its physical properties such as intensity/density in order to draw the relationship between melt viscosity, drop viscosity, and melting behaviour using the appropriate numerical models.

Outcome an Future Work

For polymer research as well as material treatment for the future and outlook, for example, watches additives also FR accomplish on the burning of polymer performances, physical and chemical characteristics, and then drips to try to stop the fire hazard, safety life, for safety measurements [9, 14] and for improved the performance of thermoplastic polymers against fire [16, 19].

The model also took into account heat flux at the deformed interface, empirical viscosity as a function of temperature, gravity flow, gasification and the residual properties present a higher dependence on the reactions [17]. The latter property might be estimated using kinetic analysis of thermogravimetric curves for both the polymeric substance and its droplets. The analysis of the listed results and plots will be automatically completed and applied by the software in next work.

The Acknowledgement

Thanks to EAPSR, UK , and the staff for their guidance and partnership.

REFERENCES

1. Beyler, C. L. and Hirschler, M. M. (2002). Thermal Decomposition of Polymers, The SFPE Handbook of Fire Protection Engineering,3rd Edition (Section 1, Chapter 7), National Fire Protection Association and The Society of Fire Protection Engineers, Quincy, MA, P.J. DiNenno, D.Drysdale, C.L. Beyler, and W.D. Walton, eds. pp.110-130.
2. ScharTEL, B. Bartholmai, M. and Knoll, U. (2006). Some comments on the main fire retardancy mechanisms in polymer nanocomposites. *Polymers for Advanced technologies* 17 (9-10): 772-777.
3. Cullis, C.F.; Hirschler, M.M. *The Combustion of Organic Polymers*; Oxford University Press: Oxford, UK, 1981.

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

4. Mastura A. Efhema, Effect of Flame Retardants and 1% Stabilizer on melting and dripping behaviour to obtain the relationship between melting and dripping behaviour of PP thermoplastic polymers due to the furnace test. Department of Physics, Libyan Journal of Basic Sciences, Special Issue for 6th International Conference for Basic Sciences and Their Applications (2023), Omer Al - Mukhtar University.
5. Butler KM. A model of melting and dripping thermoplastic objects in fire. Proceeding of the 'Fire and Materials' Conference. San Francisco USA, 31 Jan-2 Feb 2009. Interscience Communications Ltd: London; pp 341 - 352.
6. Zhu, J. Uhl, F. M. Morgan, A. B. and Wilkie, C. A. (2001). Studies on the mechanism by which the formation of nanocomposites enhances thermal stability. Chemistry of Materials 13 (12):4649-4654
7. Hu, Y.; Song, L. Chapter 8 in Flame Retardant Polymer Nanocomposites, Morgan, A.B.; Wilkie, C.A., Eds.; Wiley-Interscience: New Jersey, 2007.
8. Zhu, J. Uhl, F. M. Morgan, A. B. and Wilkie, C. A. (2001). Studies on the mechanism by which the formation of nanocomposites enhances thermal stability. Chemistry of Materials 13 (12):4649-4654
9. Mastura A. Efhima, Effect of Flame Retardants and 1% Stabilizer on Burning, Flammability Behaviour. Department of Physics, Al-Mukhtar Journal of Sciences Faculty of Science, Omer Al - Mukhtar University, 2019; 33 (2): 119-125.
10. Kashiwagi, T, Omori A and Brown J. Effects of Material Characteristics on Flame Spreading. Fire Safety Science - Proceedings of the Second International Symposium, International Association of Fire Safety Sciences, Hemisphere Publishing, New York, 1989; 107.
11. BS EN ISO 4589 - 2: 1999, Plastics - Determination of burning behaviour by oxygen index - Part 2: Ambient temperature test.
12. Wang Y, Zhang F, Chen X, Jin Y, Zhang J. Burning and dripping behaviors of polymers under the UL94 vertical burning test conditions, Fire Mater. 2010; 34(4): 203-215.
13. Kempel F, Scharfel B, Hofmann A, Butler KM, Oñate E, Idelsohn SR, Rossi R, Marti JM. Numerical simulation of polymeric materials in UL 94 test: Competition between gasification and melt flowing/dripping. Proceedings of the 12th International Interflam Conference. Interscience Communications Ltd: Nottingham, 2010; 721-730.
14. Fire Safety Aspects of Polymeric Materials` Vol. 1- Materials: state of Art, Chapter 8, A Report by National Materials Advisory Board, National Academy of Sciences, Technomic Publ. Washington, 1977.
15. Mastura A. Efhima, (2018). Effect of Flame Retardants and 1% Stabilizer on Burning, Flammability Behaviour, and Thermal Decomposition Properties Via Polypropylene Material Treatment.; Al-Mukhtar Journal of Sciences 33 (2): 119-125, 2018.
16. Lei Zhang ^a, Yiqing Dai ^b, Yu Bai ^b, Wei Chen ^c, Jihong Ye ^d, Fire performance of loaded fibre reinforced polymer multicellular composite structures with fire-resistant panels. Construction and Building Materials; Volume 296, 16 August 2021, 123733.
17. María Isabel Romero Gómez , Rui Vasco Silva , Inês Flores Colen , Jorge de Brito, Physico-Mechanical Properties of Plastic Waste-Containing Gypsum Composites Exposed to Elevated Temperature. CONBUILDMAT-D-23-06658 · 28 Pages, 21 Jun 2023.

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

18.Anja Hofmann, Andrea Klippel, Tanja Gnutzmann, Sven Kaudelka, Frederik Rabe, Influence of modern plastic furniture on the fire development in fires in homes: large-scale fire tests in living rooms. Fire and Materials. Volume 45, Issue 1; 12 November 2020.

19.Lanzón a, Francisco José Castellón b, Manuel Ayala b, Effect of the expanded perlite dose on the fire performance gypsum plasters. Construction and Building Materials; Volume 346, 5 September 2022, 128494.